

Group Actions of wreath product $\overrightarrow{S}_n$ on permutation groups

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Abstract: Wreath product $\overrightarrow{S}_n = Z_2 \wr S_n$ of type B_n is a subgroup of the symmetric group S_{2n} . In this paper we determine the group actions of wreath product $\overrightarrow{S}_n$ on a finite set. Stabilizer and orbit of a point, imprimitivity of $\overrightarrow{S}_n$ are also discussed. Also the same is illustrated with an application for $n = 3$.

Keywords group actions, symmetric groups, wreath product.

1. Introduction

[2] Wreath product is an important tool in the classification of permutation groups. It also provides a way to construct interesting examples of groups. Ghadbane N., provides some results of wreath product of groups and the notion of group actions on a set and its concepts of orbit and stabilizer.

[4] Ibrahim and Audu discussed about the conditions under which the wreath products of permutation groups are faithful, transitive and primitive.

[5] and [6] Parvathi.M and Selvaraj.C have discussed about the signed Brauer's algebra and characters of wreath product $\overrightarrow{S}_n$. Elements of wreath product $\overrightarrow{S}_n$ are represented by cyclic representations as well as by signed Brauer diagrams. A signed diagram is a graph in which every edge is labeled by plus or minus sign. An edge with plus sign is called positive edge and an edge with negative sign is called a negative edge. A graph with no horizontal edge is said to be a signed Brauer diagram in which a positive vertical edge is denoted by $\downarrow$ and a negative vertical edge is denoted by $\uparrow$.

[3] Gayathri K S, and R.Kanwar have determined 384 elements and their cycle representations of wreath product $\overrightarrow{S}_n$ for $n = 4$. using signed Brauer's algebra.

In this paper we determine the group action of wreath product $\overrightarrow{S}_n$ on a finite set. Stabilizer and orbit of a point, imprimitivity of $\overrightarrow{S}_n$ are also discussed. Also the same is illustrated with an application for $n = 3$.

1.1. Group action: [1] Let G be a group and Ω be a non-empty set. The elements of Ω be referred as points. Then for a point $\alpha \in \Omega$ and an element $g \in G$, a rule that determines a new element of Ω , denoted by $\alpha.g$, is called an action of G on Ω if the following conditions hold;

- $\alpha.1 = \alpha$ for all $\alpha \in \Omega$ and
- $(\alpha.g).h = \alpha.(gh)$ for all $\alpha \in \Omega$ and $g, h \in G$.

A group action is faithful if the only group element that fixes all the points is the identity. For example: Let G be arbitrary, and take $\Omega = G$. G act on G by right multiplication, so that $x.g = xg$ for all $x, g \in G$. This is the regular action of G on itself and it is faithful as its kernel is trivial.

If G acts on the set Ω , then G is partitioned into G -orbits, and that action is transitive if there is just one orbit: Ω itself. That is, the action of G on Ω is transitive if for every choice of points $\alpha, \beta \in \Omega$, there exists an element $g \in G$ such that $\alpha.g = \beta$.

In an arbitrary group action, the whole set Ω is a block, and so is every one-point subset of Ω . These are referred as trivial blocks. The transitive action of G on Ω is primitive if the trivial blocks are the only blocks, otherwise, the group action is imprimitive.

1.2. Stabilizer of a point: [1] If a group G acts on the set Ω and $\alpha \in \Omega$, then the set,

$$G_\alpha = \{g \in G | \alpha.g = \alpha\}$$

is called the stabilizer of the point α , and that G_α is a subgroup of G .

1.3. Orbit of a point:[1] Suppose that a group G acts on a set Ω and $\alpha \in \Omega$, then orbit of α under the given action is the set $O_\alpha = \{\alpha.g | g \in G\}$.

Distinct orbits are disjoint and if Ω is finite then $|\Omega| = \Sigma |O_\alpha|$. Also if the action is the conjugation action of G on itself then the orbits are exactly the conjugacy classes of G .

1.4. Center $Z(G)$: [1] Under the given action, the center $Z(G)$ of a group G is the set of elements $g \in G$ that commute with all $x \in G$. That is, $Z(G) = \{g \in G | gx = xg, x \in G\}$. Also, if the action is the conjugation action of G on itself, then the kernel of the conjugation action is the center $Z(G)$.

1.5. Wreath product: [1] Let G and H be two groups and G acts on a set Ω .

Let $B = \{f | f : \Omega \rightarrow H\}$. Define multiplication pointwise on B , for $f, g \in B$ and $\alpha \in \Omega$, $fg(\alpha) = f(\alpha)g(\alpha)$, then B is a group. Given $f \in B$ and $x \in G$, the function f^x on Ω is defined so that $f^x(\alpha.x) = f(\alpha)$, or equivalently, $f^x(\alpha) = f(\alpha.x^{-1})$. Now with respect to this action, $W = B \times G$ is the wreath product of H with G , and B , viewed as a subgroup of W , is called the base group of the wreath group. It is denoted as $W = H \wr G$.

2. Wreath product $\vec{S}_n$:

2.1.Theorem: Let $Z_2^n = \{f | f : \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \rightarrow Z_2\}$ be the set of all mappings from the set $n = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ into the permutation group Z_2 defined by : for any $f_1, f_2 \in Z_2^n$, $(f_1 f_2)(k) = f_1(k) + f_2(k), k \in n$, then Z_2^n is a group.

Proof:

i) Z_2^n is non-empty and closed with respect to addition for, if $f_1, f_2 \in Z_2^n$ then $f_1(k), f_2(k) \in Z_2$, for every $k \in n$.

This implies $f_1(k) + f_2(k) \in Z_2$ and $(f_1 + f_2)(k) \in Z_2$. That is $f_1 + f_2 \in Z_2^n$.

ii) Addition of functions is associative in Z_2^n .

iii) Identity element of Z_2^n is the mapping $i : \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \rightarrow Z_2$ which is given by $i(k) = (e)$, for all $k \in n$ the identity element of $(e) \in Z_2$.

iv) For every $f \in Z_2^n$ and $k \in n$, $f^{-1}(k) = -f(k)$ denoted by $f(k)^{-1}$.

Thus Z_2^n is a group with respect to operation defined.

2.2. Theorem: Let S_n act on Z_2^n as a group, then the set of ordered pairs (f, α) with $f \in Z_2^n$ and $\alpha \in S_n$ becomes a group by defining the operation as:

$$(f_1, \alpha_1)(f_2, \alpha_2) = (f_1 f_2^{\alpha_1^{-1}}, \alpha_1 \alpha_2)$$

Proof:

i) The set ordered pairs (f, α) is non-empty and is closure law follows by the definition.

ii) Let $f_1, f_2, f_3 \in Z_2^n$ and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3 \in S_n$, then

$$\begin{aligned} & [(f_1, \alpha_1)(f_2, \alpha_2)](f_3, \alpha_3) \\ &= (f_1 f_2^{\alpha_1^{-1}}, \alpha_1 \alpha_2)(f_3, \alpha_3) \\ &= (f_1 f_2^{\alpha_1^{-1}} f_3^{(\alpha_1 \alpha_2)^{-1}}, \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \alpha_3) \\ &= (f_1 f_2^{\alpha_1^{-1}} f_3^{\alpha_2^{-1} \alpha_1^{-1}}, \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \alpha_3) \\ &= (f_1 (f_2 f_3^{\alpha_2^{-1}})^{\alpha_1^{-1}}, \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \alpha_3) \\ &= (f_1, \alpha_1)(f_2 f_3^{\alpha_2^{-1}}, \alpha_2 \alpha_3) \\ &= (f_1, \alpha_1)[(f_2, \alpha_2)(f_3, \alpha_3)] \end{aligned}$$

iii) For every $f \in Z_2^n$, $f^1 = f$ and for every $\alpha \in S_n$, the mapping $f \rightarrow f^\alpha$ is an automorphism of Z_2^n . Also for the identity element $i \in Z_2^n$, $i^\alpha = i$ is the identity mapping and

$$(f^{-1})^\alpha = (f^\alpha)^{-1}.$$

Thus $(f, \alpha)(i, e)$

$$= (f(i^\alpha)^{-1}, \alpha e)$$

$$= (f(i^{-1})^\alpha, \alpha)$$

$$= (f(i)^\alpha, \alpha)$$

$$= (fi, \alpha)$$

$$= (f, \alpha).$$

Similarly, $(i, e)(f, \alpha) = (f, \alpha)$.

Thus (i, e) is the identity element.

iv) Consider,

$$(f, \alpha)((f^{-1})^\alpha, \alpha^{-1})$$

$$= (f((f^{-1})^\alpha)^{\alpha^{-1}}, \alpha \alpha^{-1})$$

$$= (f(f(f^{-1})^{\alpha \alpha^{-1}}), \alpha \alpha^{-1})$$

$$= (ff^{-1}, \alpha \alpha^{-1})$$

$$= (i, e).$$

Similarly,

$$((f^{-1})^\alpha, \alpha^{-1})(f, \alpha) = (i, e).$$

Inverse of an element exists.

Thus when S_n acts on Z_2^n , the set of all ordered pairs, Z_2^n by $S_n = \{(f, \alpha) | f \in Z_2^n, \alpha \in S_n\}$ is a group. This group is called the wreath product $Z_2^n \wr S_n$ denoted by $\overrightarrow{S}_n$. The arbitrary element (f, α) shall be denoted hereafter as $f\alpha$.

Hence we have the following definition;

2.3. Definition [4] Let $Z_2^n = \{f | f : \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \rightarrow Z_2\}$,

define $\overrightarrow{S}_n = Z_2 \wr S_n = \{(f, \pi) | f : \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \rightarrow Z_2, \pi \in S_n\}$,

where S_n is the symmetric group on n symbols. $\overrightarrow{S}_n$ is a group under composition defined by

$$(f, \pi)(f', \pi') = (ff', \pi\pi'),$$

where $(ff')(i) = f(i) + f'(i)$, $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and $f_\pi = f \circ \pi^{-1}$ for $\pi \in S_n$ and $f \in Z_2^n$. This $\vec{S}_n$ is a group of type B_n and is called the wreath product of Z_2 by S_n .

2.4. Remark The permutation groups Z_2^n and S_n are finite groups, then the wreath product $\vec{S}_n = Z_2 \wr S_n$ is a semidirect product of Z_2^n and S_n and hence a finite group whose order is given by $|\vec{S}_n| = |Z_2|^{|n|} |S_n|$.

2.5. Remark Z_2^n is a normal subgroup of $\vec{S}_n$ and S_n is a subgroup of $\vec{S}_n$.

3. Action of wreath product $\vec{S}_n$.

Z_2^n and S_n are permutation groups on the sets $A = \{1, 2\}$ and $B = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ respectively, then the action of the wreath product $\vec{S}_n$ on the set $A \times B$ is determined by the operation $(a, b)^{f\alpha} = (af(b), b\alpha)$, where $a \in A$, $b \in B$, and $\alpha \in S_n$.

3.1. Transitivity of $\vec{S}_n$ on $A \times B$.

$\vec{S}_n$ is transitive on $A \times B$ for if there exist $f\alpha \in \vec{S}_n$ such that $(a_1, b_1)^{f\alpha} = (a_2, b_2)$ where (a_1, b_1) and (a_2, b_2) are arbitrary elements of $A \times B$.

3.2. Stabilizer $\vec{S}_{n(a,b)}$ of a point (a, b) in $A \times B$.

When $\vec{S}_n$ acts on $A \times B$, the stabilizer of a point (a, b) of $A \times B$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{S}_{n(a,b)} &= \{f\alpha \mid (a, b)^{f\alpha} = (a, b)\} \\ &= \{f\alpha \mid (af(b), b\alpha) = (a, b)\} \\ &= \{f\alpha \mid (af(b) = a, b\alpha = b)\} \end{aligned}$$

3.3. Faithfulness of $\vec{S}_n$ on $A \times B$.

$\vec{S}_n$ is faithful on $A \times B$ only if Z_2^n is faithful on the set A and S_n is faithful on the set B , since $\vec{S}_{n(a,b)} = \{ie \mid (a, b)^{ie} = (ai(b), be) = (a, b)\}$.

3.4. Primitivity of $\vec{S}_n$ on $A \times B$.

$\vec{S}_n$ is primitive on $A \times B$ if and only if the stabilizer $\vec{S}_{n(a,b)}$ of any $(a, b) \in A \times B$ is a maximal subset of $\vec{S}_n$.

But, $\vec{S}_{n(a,b)}$ is not a maximal subgroup of $\vec{S}_n$ as the set $\{af(b)\}$ does not take those $f \in Z_2^n$ which do not stabilize a .

Thus $\vec{S}_{n(a,b)} = \{f\alpha \mid (af(b) = a, b\alpha = b) = (a, b)\} < Z_2^n \{ab\} < Z_2^n S_n = \vec{S}_n$. implies that $\vec{S}_n$ is imprimitive on $A \times B$.

3.5. Centre of $\vec{S}_n = Z(\vec{S}_n)$,

The centre $Z(\vec{S}_n) = \{f\alpha \mid (f\alpha)(f_1\alpha_1) = (f_1\alpha_1)(f\alpha), f_1\alpha_1 \in \vec{S}_n\}$.

$f\alpha \in Z(\vec{S}_n)$ if and only if

$$(3.5.1) \quad ff_1^{\alpha^{-1}}\alpha\alpha_1 = f_1f^{\alpha^{-1}}\alpha_1\alpha \text{ for all } f_1 \in Z_2^n \text{ and } \alpha_1 \in S_n.$$

Take $f_1 = i$ in (3.5.1), then

$$f\alpha\alpha_1 = f^{\alpha^{-1}}\alpha_1\alpha \text{ for all } \alpha_1 \in S_n.$$

Take $\alpha_1 = e$, in (3.5.1) then

$$ff_1^{\alpha^{-1}}\alpha = f_1f\alpha$$

From (3.5.1), it follows that,

for $f\alpha$ to be in $Z(\vec{S}_n)$ it is necessary that $\alpha \in Z(S_n)$.

4. Application:

Consider the permutation groups $Z_2 = \{(1), (12)\}$ and $S_3 = \{(1), (12), (13), (23), (123), (132)\}$ on the sets $A = \{1, 2\}$ and $B = \{1, 2, 3\}$.

Let $Z_2^B = \{f|f : B \rightarrow Z_2\}$, then $|Z_2^B| = 2^3 = 8$. The mappings are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f_1 &: 1 \rightarrow (1), 2 \rightarrow (1), 3 \rightarrow (1) \\ f_2 &: 1 \rightarrow (1), 2 \rightarrow (1), 3 \rightarrow (12) \\ f_3 &: 1 \rightarrow (1), 2 \rightarrow (12), 3 \rightarrow (1) \\ f_4 &: 1 \rightarrow (12), 2 \rightarrow (1), 3 \rightarrow (1) \\ f_5 &: 1 \rightarrow (12), 2 \rightarrow (12), 3 \rightarrow (12) \\ f_6 &: 1 \rightarrow (12), 2 \rightarrow (12), 3 \rightarrow (1) \\ f_7 &: 1 \rightarrow (12), 2 \rightarrow (1), 3 \rightarrow (12) \\ f_8 &: 1 \rightarrow (1), 2 \rightarrow (12), 3 \rightarrow (12) \end{aligned}$$

Z_2^3 is a group with respect to the operations

$$f_1 f_2(b) = f_1(b) + f_2(b) \text{ where } b \in B.$$

Action of S_3 on Z_2^3 is given by

$$f^\alpha(b) = f(b\alpha^{-1}) \text{ where } \alpha \in S_3, b \in B.$$

Now, $\vec{S}_3 = Z_2 \wr S_3$ is a semidirect product given by

$$\vec{S}_3 = \{f\alpha | f \in Z_2^B, \alpha \in S_3\}.$$

Now, $\vec{S}_3$ is group with respect to the operation

$$(f_1\alpha_1)(f_2\alpha_2) = (f_1 f_2^{\alpha_1^{-1}})(\alpha_1\alpha_2)$$

Accordingly,

$$\alpha_1 = (1), \alpha_2 = (12), \alpha_3 = (13), \alpha_4 = (23), \alpha_5 = (123), \alpha_6 = (132).$$

Then the elements of $\vec{S}_3$ are

$$\{(f_1\alpha_1), (f_2\alpha_1), (f_3\alpha_1), (f_4\alpha_1), (f_5\alpha_1), (f_6\alpha_1), (f_7\alpha_1), (f_8\alpha_1), (f_1\alpha_2), (f_2\alpha_2), (f_3\alpha_2), (f_4\alpha_2), (f_5\alpha_2), (f_6\alpha_2), (f_7\alpha_2), (f_8\alpha_2), (f_1\alpha_3), (f_2\alpha_3), (f_3\alpha_3), (f_4\alpha_3), (f_5\alpha_3), (f_6\alpha_3), (f_7\alpha_3), (f_8\alpha_3), (f_1\alpha_4), (f_2\alpha_4), (f_3\alpha_4), (f_4\alpha_4), (f_5\alpha_4), (f_6\alpha_4), (f_7\alpha_4), (f_8\alpha_4), (f_1\alpha_5), (f_2\alpha_5), (f_3\alpha_5), (f_4\alpha_5), (f_5\alpha_5), (f_6\alpha_5), (f_7\alpha_5), (f_8\alpha_5), (f_1\alpha_6), (f_2\alpha_6), (f_3\alpha_6), (f_4\alpha_6), (f_5\alpha_6), (f_6\alpha_6), (f_7\alpha_6), (f_8\alpha_6)\}$$

Define action of $\vec{S}_3$ on $A \times B$ as

$$(a, b)^{f\alpha} = (af(b), b\alpha)$$

where

$$A \times B = \{(1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3)\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (1, 1)^{f_1\alpha_1} &= (1f_1(1), 1\alpha_1) = (1(1), 1(1)) = (1, 1) \\ (1, 2)^{f_1\alpha_1} &= (1f_1(2), 2\alpha_1) = (1(1), 2(1)) = (1, 2) \\ (1, 3)^{f_1\alpha_1} &= (1f_1(3), 3\alpha_1) = (1(1), 3(1)) = (1, 3) \\ (2, 1)^{f_1\alpha_1} &= (2f_1(1), 1\alpha_1) = (2(1), 1(1)) = (2, 1) \\ (2, 2)^{f_1\alpha_1} &= (2f_1(2), 2\alpha_1) = (2(1), 2(1)) = (2, 2) \\ (2, 3)^{f_1\alpha_1} &= (2f_1(3), 3\alpha_1) = (2(1), 3(1)) = (2, 3) \\ (1, 1)^{f_2\alpha_1} &= (1f_2(1), 1\alpha_1) = (1(1), 1(1)) = (1, 1) \\ (1, 2)^{f_2\alpha_1} &= (1f_2(2), 2\alpha_1) = (1(1), 2(1)) = (1, 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(1, 3)f_2^{\alpha_1} &= (1f_2(3), 3\alpha_1) = (1(12), 3(1)) = (2, 3) \\
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(2, 1)f_2^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_2(1), 1\alpha_2) = (2(1), 1(12)) = (2, 2) \\
(2, 2)f_2^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_2(2), 2\alpha_2) = (2(1), 2(12)) = (2, 1) \\
(2, 3)f_2^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_2(3), 3\alpha_2) = (2(12), 3(12)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 1)f_3^{\alpha_2} &= (1f_3(1), 1\alpha_2) = (1(1), 1(12)) = (1, 2) \\
(1, 2)f_3^{\alpha_2} &= (1f_3(2), 2\alpha_2) = (1(12), 2(12)) = (2, 1) \\
(1, 3)f_3^{\alpha_2} &= (1f_3(3), 3\alpha_2) = (1(1), 3(12)) = (1, 3) \\
(2, 1)f_3^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_3(1), 1\alpha_2) = (2(1), 1(12)) = (2, 2) \\
(2, 2)f_3^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_3(2), 2\alpha_2) = (2(12), 2(12)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 3)f_3^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_3(3), 3\alpha_2) = (2(1), 3(12)) = (2, 3) \\
(1, 1)f_4^{\alpha_2} &= (1f_4(1), 1\alpha_2) = (1(12), 1(12)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 2)f_4^{\alpha_2} &= (1f_4(2), 2\alpha_2) = (1(1), 2(12)) = (1, 1) \\
(1, 3)f_4^{\alpha_2} &= (1f_4(3), 3\alpha_2) = (1(1), 3(12)) = (1, 3) \\
(2, 1)f_4^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_4(1), 1\alpha_2) = (2(12), 1(12)) = (1, 2) \\
(2, 2)f_4^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_4(2), 2\alpha_2) = (2(1), 2(12)) = (2, 1) \\
(2, 3)f_4^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_4(3), 3\alpha_2) = (2(1), 3(12)) = (2, 3) \\
(1, 1)f_5^{\alpha_2} &= (1f_5(1), 1\alpha_2) = (1(12), 1(12)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 2)f_5^{\alpha_2} &= (1f_5(2), 2\alpha_2) = (1(12), 2(12)) = (2, 1) \\
(1, 3)f_5^{\alpha_2} &= (1f_5(3), 3\alpha_2) = (1(12), 3(12)) = (2, 3) \\
(2, 1)f_5^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_5(1), 1\alpha_2) = (2(12), 1(12)) = (1, 2) \\
(2, 2)f_5^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_5(2), 2\alpha_2) = (2(12), 2(12)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 3)f_5^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_5(3), 3\alpha_2) = (2(12), 3(12)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 1)f_6^{\alpha_2} &= (1f_6(1), 1\alpha_2) = (1(12), 1(12)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 2)f_6^{\alpha_2} &= (1f_6(2), 2\alpha_2) = (1(12), 2(12)) = (2, 1) \\
(1, 3)f_6^{\alpha_2} &= (1f_6(3), 3\alpha_2) = (1(1), 3(12)) = (1, 3) \\
(2, 1)f_6^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_6(1), 1\alpha_2) = (2(12), 1(12)) = (1, 2) \\
(2, 2)f_6^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_6(2), 2\alpha_2) = (2(12), 2(12)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 3)f_6^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_6(3), 3\alpha_2) = (2(1), 3(12)) = (2, 3) \\
(1, 1)f_7^{\alpha_2} &= (1f_7(1), 1\alpha_2) = (1(12), 1(12)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 2)f_7^{\alpha_2} &= (1f_7(2), 2\alpha_2) = (1(1), 2(12)) = (1, 1) \\
(1, 3)f_7^{\alpha_2} &= (1f_7(3), 3\alpha_2) = (1(12), 3(12)) = (2, 3) \\
(2, 1)f_7^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_7(1), 1\alpha_2) = (2(12), 1(12)) = (1, 2) \\
(2, 2)f_7^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_7(2), 2\alpha_2) = (2(1), 2(12)) = (2, 1) \\
(2, 3)f_7^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_7(3), 3\alpha_2) = (2(12), 3(12)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 1)f_8^{\alpha_2} &= (1f_8(1), 1\alpha_2) = (1(1), 1(12)) = (1, 2) \\
(1, 2)f_8^{\alpha_2} &= (1f_8(2), 2\alpha_2) = (1(12), 2(12)) = (2, 1) \\
(1, 3)f_8^{\alpha_2} &= (1f_8(3), 3\alpha_2) = (1(12), 3(12)) = (2, 3) \\
(2, 1)f_8^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_8(1), 1\alpha_2) = (2(1), 1(12)) = (2, 2) \\
(2, 2)f_8^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_8(2), 2\alpha_2) = (2(12), 2(12)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 3)f_8^{\alpha_2} &= (2f_8(3), 3\alpha_2) = (2(12), 3(12)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 1)f_1^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_1(1), 1\alpha_3) = (1(1), 1(13)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 2)f_1^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_1(2), 2\alpha_3) = (1(1), 2(13)) = (1, 2) \\
(1, 3)f_1^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_1(3), 3\alpha_3) = (1(1), 3(13)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 1)f_1^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_1(1), 1\alpha_3) = (2(1), 1(13)) = (2, 3) \\
(2, 2)f_1^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_1(2), 2\alpha_3) = (2(1), 2(13)) = (2, 2) \\
(2, 3)f_1^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_1(3), 3\alpha_3) = (2(1), 3(13)) = (2, 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(1, 1)f_2^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_2(1), 1\alpha_3) = (1(1), 1(13)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 2)f_2^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_2(2), 2\alpha_3) = (1(1), 2(13)) = (1, 2) \\
(1, 3)f_2^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_2(3), 3\alpha_3) = (1(12), 3(13)) = (2, 1) \\
(2, 1)f_2^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_2(1), 1\alpha_3) = (2(1), 1(13)) = (2, 3) \\
(2, 2)f_2^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_2(2), 2\alpha_3) = (2(1), 2(13)) = (2, 2) \\
(2, 3)f_2^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_2(3), 3\alpha_3) = (2(12), 3(13)) = (1, 1) \\
(1, 1)f_3^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_3(1), 1\alpha_3) = (1(1), 1(13)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 2)f_3^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_3(2), 2\alpha_3) = (1(12), 2(13)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 3)f_3^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_3(3), 3\alpha_3) = (1(1), 3(13)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 1)f_3^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_3(1), 1\alpha_3) = (2(1), 1(13)) = (2, 3) \\
(2, 2)f_3^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_3(2), 2\alpha_3) = (2(12), 2(13)) = (1, 2) \\
(2, 3)f_3^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_3(3), 3\alpha_3) = (2(1), 3(13)) = (2, 1) \\
(1, 1)f_4^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_4(1), 1\alpha_3) = (1(12), 1(13)) = (2, 3) \\
(1, 2)f_4^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_4(2), 2\alpha_3) = (1(1), 2(13)) = (1, 2) \\
(1, 3)f_4^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_4(3), 3\alpha_3) = (1(1), 3(13)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 1)f_4^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_4(1), 1\alpha_3) = (2(12), 1(13)) = (1, 3) \\
(2, 2)f_4^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_4(2), 2\alpha_3) = (2(1), 2(13)) = (2, 2) \\
(2, 3)f_4^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_4(3), 3\alpha_3) = (2(1), 3(13)) = (2, 1) \\
(1, 1)f_5^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_5(1), 1\alpha_3) = (1(12), 1(13)) = (2, 3) \\
(1, 2)f_5^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_5(2), 2\alpha_3) = (1(12), 2(13)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 3)f_5^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_5(3), 3\alpha_3) = (1(12), 3(13)) = (2, 1) \\
(2, 1)f_5^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_5(1), 1\alpha_3) = (2(12), 1(13)) = (1, 3) \\
(2, 2)f_5^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_5(2), 2\alpha_3) = (2(12), 2(13)) = (1, 2) \\
(2, 3)f_5^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_5(3), 3\alpha_3) = (2(12), 3(13)) = (1, 1) \\
(1, 1)f_6^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_6(1), 1\alpha_3) = (1(12), 1(13)) = (2, 3) \\
(1, 2)f_6^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_6(2), 2\alpha_3) = (1(12), 2(13)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 3)f_6^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_6(3), 3\alpha_3) = (1(1), 3(13)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 1)f_6^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_6(1), 1\alpha_3) = (2(12), 1(13)) = (1, 3) \\
(2, 2)f_6^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_6(2), 2\alpha_3) = (2(12), 2(13)) = (1, 2) \\
(2, 3)f_6^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_6(3), 3\alpha_3) = (2(1), 3(13)) = (2, 1) \\
(1, 1)f_7^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_7(1), 1\alpha_3) = (1(12), 1(13)) = (2, 3) \\
(1, 2)f_7^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_7(2), 2\alpha_3) = (1(1), 2(13)) = (1, 2) \\
(1, 3)f_7^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_7(3), 3\alpha_3) = (1(12), 3(13)) = (2, 1) \\
(2, 1)f_7^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_7(1), 1\alpha_3) = (2(12), 1(13)) = (1, 3) \\
(2, 2)f_7^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_7(2), 2\alpha_3) = (2(1), 2(13)) = (2, 2) \\
(2, 3)f_7^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_7(3), 3\alpha_3) = (2(12), 3(13)) = (1, 1) \\
(1, 1)f_8^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_8(1), 1\alpha_3) = (1(1), 1(13)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 2)f_8^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_8(2), 2\alpha_3) = (1(12), 2(13)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 3)f_8^{\alpha_3} &= (1f_8(3), 3\alpha_3) = (1(12), 3(13)) = (2, 1) \\
(2, 1)f_8^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_8(1), 1\alpha_3) = (2(1), 1(13)) = (2, 3) \\
(2, 2)f_8^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_8(2), 2\alpha_3) = (2(12), 2(13)) = (1, 2) \\
(2, 3)f_8^{\alpha_3} &= (2f_8(3), 3\alpha_3) = (2(12), 3(13)) = (1, 1) \\
(1, 1)f_1^{\alpha_4} &= (1f_1(1), 1\alpha_4) = (1(1), 1(23)) = (1, 1) \\
(1, 2)f_1^{\alpha_4} &= (1f_1(2), 2\alpha_4) = (1(1), 2(23)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 3)f_1^{\alpha_4} &= (1f_1(3), 3\alpha_4) = (1(1), 3(23)) = (1, 2) \\
(2, 1)f_1^{\alpha_4} &= (2f_1(1), 1\alpha_4) = (2(1), 1(23)) = (2, 1) \\
(2, 2)f_1^{\alpha_4} &= (2f_1(2), 2\alpha_4) = (2(1), 2(23)) = (2, 3)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(2, 3)f_{1\alpha_4} &= (2f_1(3), 3\alpha_4) = (2(1), 3(23)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 1)f_{2\alpha_4} &= (1f_2(1), 1\alpha_4) = (1(1), 1(23)) = (1, 1) \\
(1, 2)f_{2\alpha_4} &= (1f_2(2), 2\alpha_4) = (1(1), 2(23)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 3)f_{2\alpha_4} &= (1f_2(3), 3\alpha_4) = (1(12), 3(23)) = (2, 2) \\
(2, 1)f_{2\alpha_4} &= (2f_2(1), 1\alpha_4) = (2(1), 1(23)) = (2, 1) \\
(2, 2)f_{2\alpha_4} &= (2f_2(2), 2\alpha_4) = (2(1), 2(23)) = (2, 3) \\
(2, 3)f_{2\alpha_4} &= (2f_2(3), 3\alpha_4) = (2(12), 3(23)) = (1, 2) \\
(1, 1)f_{3\alpha_4} &= (1f_3(1), 1\alpha_4) = (1(1), 1(23)) = (1, 1) \\
(1, 2)f_{3\alpha_4} &= (1f_3(2), 2\alpha_4) = (1(12), 2(23)) = (2, 3) \\
(1, 3)f_{3\alpha_4} &= (1f_3(3), 3\alpha_4) = (1(1), 3(23)) = (1, 2) \\
(2, 1)f_{3\alpha_4} &= (2f_3(1), 1\alpha_4) = (2(1), 1(23)) = (2, 1) \\
(2, 2)f_{3\alpha_4} &= (2f_3(2), 2\alpha_4) = (2(12)2(23)) = (1, 3) \\
(2, 3)f_{3\alpha_4} &= (2f_3(3), 3\alpha_4) = (2(1), 3(23)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 1)f_{4\alpha_4} &= (1f_4(1), 1\alpha_4) = (1(12), 1(23)) = (2, 1) \\
(1, 2)f_{4\alpha_4} &= (1f_4(2), 2\alpha_4) = (1(1), 2(23)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 3)f_{4\alpha_4} &= (1f_4(3), 3\alpha_4) = (1(1), 3(23)) = (1, 2) \\
(2, 1)f_{4\alpha_4} &= (2f_4(1), 1\alpha_4) = (2(12), 1(23)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 2)f_{4\alpha_4} &= (2f_4(2), 2\alpha_4) = (2(1), 2(23)) = (2, 3) \\
(2, 3)f_{4\alpha_4} &= (2f_4(3), 3\alpha_4) = (2(1), 3(23)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 1)f_{5\alpha_4} &= (1f_5(1), 1\alpha_4) = (1(12), 1(23)) = (2, 1) \\
(1, 2)f_{5\alpha_4} &= (1f_5(2), 2\alpha_4) = (1(12), 2(23)) = (2, 3) \\
(1, 3)f_{5\alpha_4} &= (1f_5(3), 3\alpha_4) = (1(12), 3(23)) = (2, 2) \\
(2, 1)f_{5\alpha_4} &= (2f_5(1), 1\alpha_4) = (2(12), 1(23)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 2)f_{5\alpha_4} &= (2f_5(2), 2\alpha_4) = (2(12), 2(23)) = (1, 3) \\
(2, 3)f_{5\alpha_4} &= (2f_5(3), 3\alpha_4) = (2(12), 3(23)) = (1, 2) \\
(1, 1)f_{6\alpha_4} &= (1f_6(1), 1\alpha_4) = (1(12), 1(23)) = (2, 1) \\
(1, 2)f_{6\alpha_4} &= (1f_6(2), 2\alpha_4) = (1(12), 2(23)) = (2, 3) \\
(1, 3)f_{6\alpha_4} &= (1f_6(3), 3\alpha_4) = (1(1), 3(23)) = (1, 2) \\
(2, 1)f_{6\alpha_4} &= (2f_6(1), 1\alpha_4) = (2(12), 1(23)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 2)f_{6\alpha_4} &= (2f_6(2), 2\alpha_4) = (2(12), 2(23)) = (1, 3) \\
(2, 3)f_{6\alpha_4} &= (2f_6(3), 3\alpha_4) = (2(1), 3(23)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 1)f_{7\alpha_4} &= (1f_7(1), 1\alpha_4) = (1(12), 1(23)) = (2, 1) \\
(1, 2)f_{7\alpha_4} &= (1f_7(2), 2\alpha_4) = (1(1), 2(23)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 3)f_{7\alpha_4} &= (1f_7(3), 3\alpha_4) = (1(12), 3(23)) = (2, 2) \\
(2, 1)f_{7\alpha_4} &= (2f_7(1), 1\alpha_4) = (2(12), 1(23)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 2)f_{7\alpha_4} &= (2f_7(2), 2\alpha_4) = (2(1), 2(23)) = (2, 3) \\
(2, 3)f_{7\alpha_4} &= (2f_7(3), 3\alpha_4) = (2(12), 3(23)) = (1, 2) \\
(1, 1)f_{8\alpha_4} &= (1f_8(1), 1\alpha_4) = (1(1), 1(23)) = (1, 1) \\
(1, 2)f_{8\alpha_4} &= (1f_8(2), 2\alpha_4) = (1(12), 2(23)) = (2, 3) \\
(1, 3)f_{8\alpha_4} &= (1f_8(3), 3\alpha_4) = (1(12), 3(23)) = (2, 2) \\
(2, 1)f_{8\alpha_4} &= (2f_8(1), 1\alpha_4) = (2(1), 1(23)) = (2, 1) \\
(2, 2)f_{8\alpha_4} &= (2f_8(2), 2\alpha_4) = (2(12), 2(23)) = (1, 3) \\
(2, 3)f_{8\alpha_4} &= (2f_8(3), 3\alpha_4) = (2(12), 3(23)) = (1, 2) \\
(1, 1)f_{1\alpha_5} &= (1f_1(1), 1\alpha_5) = (1(1), 1(123)) = (1, 2) \\
(1, 2)f_{1\alpha_5} &= (1f_1(2), 2\alpha_5) = (1(1), 2(123)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 3)f_{1\alpha_5} &= (1f_1(3), 3\alpha_5) = (1(1), 3(123)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 1)f_{1\alpha_5} &= (2f_1(1), 1\alpha_5) = (2(1), 1(123)) = (2, 2)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(2, 2)^{f_1\alpha_5} &= (2f_1(2), 2\alpha_5) = (2(1), 2(123)) = (2, 3) \\
(2, 3)^{f_1\alpha_5} &= (2f_1(3), 3\alpha_5) = (2(1), 3(123)) = (2, 1) \\
(1, 1)^{f_2\alpha_5} &= (1f_2(1), 1\alpha_5) = (1(1), 1(123)) = (1, 2) \\
(1, 2)^{f_2\alpha_5} &= (1f_2(2), 2\alpha_5) = (1(1), 2(123)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 3)^{f_2\alpha_5} &= (1f_2(3), 3\alpha_5) = (1(12), 3(123)) = (2, 1) \\
(2, 1)^{f_2\alpha_5} &= (2f_2(1), 1\alpha_5) = (2(1), 1(123)) = (2, 2) \\
(2, 2)^{f_2\alpha_5} &= (2f_2(2), 2\alpha_5) = (2(1), 2(123)) = (2, 3) \\
(2, 3)^{f_2\alpha_5} &= (2f_2(3), 3\alpha_5) = (2(12), 3(123)) = (1, 1) \\
(1, 1)^{f_3\alpha_5} &= (1f_3(1), 1\alpha_5) = (1(1), 1(123)) = (1, 2) \\
(1, 2)^{f_3\alpha_5} &= (1f_3(2), 2\alpha_5) = (1(12), 2(123)) = (2, 3) \\
(1, 3)^{f_3\alpha_5} &= (1f_3(3), 3\alpha_5) = (1(1), 3(123)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 1)^{f_3\alpha_5} &= (2f_3(1), 1\alpha_5) = (2(1), 1(123)) = (2, 2) \\
(2, 2)^{f_3\alpha_5} &= (2f_3(2), 2\alpha_5) = (2(12), 2(123)) = (1, 3) \\
(2, 3)^{f_3\alpha_5} &= (2f_3(3), 3\alpha_5) = (2(1), 3(123)) = (2, 1) \\
(1, 1)^{f_4\alpha_5} &= (1f_4(1), 1\alpha_5) = (1(12), 1(123)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 2)^{f_4\alpha_5} &= (1f_4(2), 2\alpha_5) = (1(1), 2(123)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 3)^{f_4\alpha_5} &= (1f_4(3), 3\alpha_5) = (1(1), 3(123)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 1)^{f_4\alpha_5} &= (2f_4(1), 1\alpha_5) = (2(12), 1(123)) = (1, 2) \\
(2, 2)^{f_4\alpha_5} &= (2f_4(2), 2\alpha_5) = (2(1), 2(123)) = (2, 3) \\
(2, 3)^{f_4\alpha_5} &= (2f_4(3), 3\alpha_5) = (2(1), 3(123)) = (2, 1) \\
(1, 1)^{f_5\alpha_5} &= (1f_5(1), 1\alpha_5) = (1(12), 1(123)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 2)^{f_5\alpha_5} &= (1f_5(2), 2\alpha_5) = (1(12), 2(123)) = (2, 3) \\
(1, 3)^{f_5\alpha_5} &= (1f_5(3), 3\alpha_5) = (1(12), 3(123)) = (2, 1) \\
(2, 1)^{f_5\alpha_5} &= (2f_5(1), 1\alpha_5) = (2(12), 1(123)) = (1, 2) \\
(2, 2)^{f_5\alpha_5} &= (2f_5(2), 2\alpha_5) = (2(12), 2(123)) = (1, 3) \\
(2, 3)^{f_5\alpha_5} &= (2f_5(3), 3\alpha_5) = (2(12), 3(123)) = (1, 1) \\
(1, 1)^{f_6\alpha_5} &= (1f_6(1), 1\alpha_5) = (1(12), 1(123)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 2)^{f_6\alpha_5} &= (1f_6(2), 2\alpha_5) = (1(12), 2(123)) = (2, 3) \\
(1, 3)^{f_6\alpha_5} &= (1f_6(3), 3\alpha_5) = (1(1), 3(123)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 1)^{f_6\alpha_5} &= (2f_6(1), 1\alpha_5) = (2(12), 1(123)) = (1, 2) \\
(2, 2)^{f_6\alpha_5} &= (2f_6(2), 2\alpha_5) = (2(12), 2(123)) = (1, 3) \\
(2, 3)^{f_6\alpha_5} &= (2f_6(3), 3\alpha_5) = (2(1), 3(123)) = (2, 1) \\
(1, 1)^{f_7\alpha_5} &= (1f_7(1), 1\alpha_5) = (1(12), 1(123)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 2)^{f_7\alpha_5} &= (1f_7(2), 2\alpha_5) = (1(1), 2(123)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 3)^{f_7\alpha_5} &= (1f_7(3), 3\alpha_5) = (1(12), 3(123)) = (2, 1) \\
(2, 1)^{f_7\alpha_5} &= (2f_7(1), 1\alpha_5) = (2(12), 1(123)) = (1, 2) \\
(2, 2)^{f_7\alpha_5} &= (2f_7(2), 2\alpha_5) = (2(1), 2(123)) = (2, 3) \\
(2, 3)^{f_7\alpha_5} &= (2f_7(3), 3\alpha_5) = (2(12), 3(123)) = (1, 1) \\
(1, 1)^{f_8\alpha_5} &= (1f_8(1), 1\alpha_5) = (1(1), 1(123)) = (1, 2) \\
(1, 2)^{f_8\alpha_5} &= (1f_8(2), 2\alpha_5) = (1(12), 2(123)) = (2, 3) \\
(1, 3)^{f_8\alpha_5} &= (1f_8(3), 3\alpha_5) = (1(12), 3(123)) = (2, 1) \\
(2, 1)^{f_8\alpha_5} &= (2f_8(1), 1\alpha_5) = (2(1), 1(123)) = (2, 2) \\
(2, 2)^{f_8\alpha_5} &= (2f_8(2), 2\alpha_5) = (2(12), 2(123)) = (1, 3) \\
(2, 3)^{f_8\alpha_5} &= (2f_8(3), 3\alpha_5) = (2(12), 3(123)) = (1, 1) \\
(1, 1)^{f_1\alpha_6} &= (1f_1(1), 1\alpha_6) = (1(1), 1(132)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 2)^{f_1\alpha_6} &= (1f_1(2), 2\alpha_6) = (1(1), 2(132)) = (1, 1) \\
(1, 3)^{f_1\alpha_6} &= (1f_1(3), 3\alpha_6) = (1(1), 3(132)) = (1, 2)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(2, 1)^{f_1\alpha_6} &= (2f_1(1), 1\alpha_6) = (2(1), 1(132)) = (2, 3) \\
(2, 2)^{f_1\alpha_6} &= (2f_1(2), 2\alpha_6) = (2(1), 2(132)) = (2, 1) \\
(2, 3)^{f_1\alpha_6} &= (2f_1(3), 3\alpha_6) = (2(1), 3(132)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 1)^{f_2\alpha_6} &= (1f_2(1), 1\alpha_6) = (1(1), 1(132)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 2)^{f_2\alpha_6} &= (1f_2(2), 2\alpha_6) = (1(1), 2(132)) = (1, 1) \\
(1, 3)^{f_2\alpha_6} &= (1f_2(3), 3\alpha_6) = (1(12), 3(132)) = (2, 2) \\
(2, 1)^{f_2\alpha_6} &= (2f_2(1), 1\alpha_6) = (2(1), 1(132)) = (2, 3) \\
(2, 2)^{f_2\alpha_6} &= (2f_2(2), 2\alpha_6) = (2(1), 2(132)) = (2, 1) \\
(2, 3)^{f_2\alpha_6} &= (2f_2(3), 3\alpha_6) = (2(12), 3(132)) = (1, 2) \\
(1, 1)^{f_3\alpha_6} &= (1f_3(1), 1\alpha_6) = (1(1), 1(132)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 2)^{f_3\alpha_6} &= (1f_3(2), 2\alpha_6) = (1(12), 2(132)) = (2, 1) \\
(1, 3)^{f_3\alpha_6} &= (1f_3(3), 3\alpha_6) = (1(1), 3(132)) = (1, 2) \\
(2, 1)^{f_3\alpha_6} &= (2f_3(1), 1\alpha_6) = (2(1), 1(132)) = (2, 3) \\
(2, 2)^{f_3\alpha_6} &= (2f_3(2), 2\alpha_6) = (2(12), 2(132)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 3)^{f_3\alpha_6} &= (2f_3(3), 3\alpha_6) = (2(1), 3(132)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 1)^{f_4\alpha_6} &= (1f_4(1), 1\alpha_6) = (1(12), 1(132)) = (2, 3) \\
(1, 2)^{f_4\alpha_6} &= (1f_4(2), 2\alpha_6) = (1(1), 2(132)) = (1, 1) \\
(1, 3)^{f_4\alpha_6} &= (1f_4(3), 3\alpha_6) = (1(1), 3(132)) = (1, 2) \\
(2, 1)^{f_4\alpha_6} &= (2f_4(1), 1\alpha_6) = (2(12), 1(132)) = (1, 3) \\
(2, 2)^{f_4\alpha_6} &= (2f_4(2), 2\alpha_6) = (2(1), 2(132)) = (2, 1) \\
(2, 3)^{f_4\alpha_6} &= (2f_4(3), 3\alpha_6) = (2(1), 3(132)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 1)^{f_5\alpha_6} &= (1f_5(1), 1\alpha_6) = (1(12), 1(132)) = (2, 3) \\
(1, 2)^{f_5\alpha_6} &= (1f_5(2), 2\alpha_6) = (1(12), 2(132)) = (2, 1) \\
(1, 3)^{f_5\alpha_6} &= (1f_5(3), 3\alpha_6) = (1(12), 3(132)) = (2, 2) \\
(2, 1)^{f_5\alpha_6} &= (2f_5(1), 1\alpha_6) = (2(12), 1(132)) = (1, 3) \\
(2, 2)^{f_5\alpha_6} &= (2f_5(2), 2\alpha_6) = (2(12), 2(132)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 3)^{f_5\alpha_6} &= (2f_5(3), 3\alpha_6) = (2(12), 3(132)) = (1, 2) \\
(1, 1)^{f_6\alpha_6} &= (1f_6(1), 1\alpha_6) = (1(12), 1(132)) = (2, 3) \\
(1, 2)^{f_6\alpha_6} &= (1f_6(2), 2\alpha_6) = (1(12), 2(132)) = (2, 1) \\
(1, 3)^{f_6\alpha_6} &= (1f_6(3), 3\alpha_6) = (1(1), 3(132)) = (1, 2) \\
(2, 1)^{f_6\alpha_6} &= (2f_6(1), 1\alpha_6) = (2(12), 1(132)) = (1, 3) \\
(2, 2)^{f_6\alpha_6} &= (2f_6(2), 2\alpha_6) = (2(12), 2(132)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 3)^{f_6\alpha_6} &= (2f_6(3), 3\alpha_6) = (2(1), 3(132)) = (2, 2) \\
(1, 1)^{f_7\alpha_6} &= (1f_7(1), 1\alpha_6) = (1(12), 1(132)) = (2, 3) \\
(1, 2)^{f_7\alpha_6} &= (1f_7(2), 2\alpha_6) = (1(1), 2(132)) = (1, 1) \\
(1, 3)^{f_7\alpha_6} &= (1f_7(3), 3\alpha_6) = (1(12), 3(132)) = (2, 2) \\
(2, 1)^{f_7\alpha_6} &= (2f_7(1), 1\alpha_6) = (2(12), 1(132)) = (1, 3) \\
(2, 2)^{f_7\alpha_6} &= (2f_7(2), 2\alpha_6) = (2(1), 2(132)) = (2, 1) \\
(2, 3)^{f_7\alpha_6} &= (2f_7(3), 3\alpha_6) = (2(12), 3(132)) = (1, 2) \\
(1, 1)^{f_8\alpha_6} &= (1f_8(1), 1\alpha_6) = (1(1), 1(132)) = (1, 3) \\
(1, 2)^{f_8\alpha_6} &= (1f_8(2), 2\alpha_6) = (1(12), 2(132)) = (2, 1) \\
(1, 3)^{f_8\alpha_6} &= (1f_8(3), 3\alpha_6) = (1(12), 3(132)) = (2, 2) \\
(2, 1)^{f_8\alpha_6} &= (2f_8(1), 1\alpha_6) = (2(1), 1(132)) = (2, 3) \\
(2, 2)^{f_8\alpha_6} &= (2f_8(2), 2\alpha_6) = (2(12), 2(132)) = (1, 1) \\
(2, 3)^{f_8\alpha_6} &= (2f_8(3), 3\alpha_6) = (2(12), 3(132)) = (1, 2)
\end{aligned}$$

Rename the points as

$$(1, 1) \rightarrow 1, (1, 2) \rightarrow 2, (1, 3) \rightarrow 3,$$

$$(2, 1) \rightarrow 4, (2, 2) \rightarrow 5, (2, 3) \rightarrow 6,$$

we get the cyclic representation of the elements as

$$(A \times B)^{f_{1\alpha_1}} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (e)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_{2\alpha_1}} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (36)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_{3\alpha_1}} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (25)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_{4\alpha_1}} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (14)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_{5\alpha_1}} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (14)(25)(36)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_{6\alpha_1}} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (14)(25)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_{7\alpha_1}} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (14)(36)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_{8\alpha_1}} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (25)(36)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_{1\alpha_2}} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (12)(45)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_{2\alpha_2}} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (12)(45)(36)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_{3\alpha_2}} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (1245)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_{4\alpha_2}} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (1542)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_{5\alpha_2}} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (15)(42)(36)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_{6\alpha_2}} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (15)(42)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_{7\alpha_2}} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (1542)(36)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_{8\alpha_2}} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (1245)(36)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_{1\alpha_3}} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (13)(46)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_{2\alpha_3}} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (1346)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_3\alpha_3} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (13)(46)(25)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_4\alpha_3} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (1643)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_5\alpha_3} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (16)(43)(25)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_6\alpha_3} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (1643)(25)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_7\alpha_3} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (16)(43)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_8\alpha_3} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (1346)(25)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_1\alpha_4} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (23)(56)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_2\alpha_4} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (2356)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_3\alpha_4} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (2653)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_4\alpha_4} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (14)(23)(56)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_5\alpha_4} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (14)(26)(53)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_6\alpha_4} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (14)(2653)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_7\alpha_4} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (14)(2356)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_8\alpha_4} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (26)(53)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_1\alpha_5} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (123)(456)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_2\alpha_5} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (123456)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_3\alpha_5} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (126453)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_4\alpha_5} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (156423)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_5\alpha_5} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (153426)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_6\alpha_5} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (153)(426)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_7\alpha_5} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (156)(423)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_8\alpha_5} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (126)(453)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_1\alpha_6} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (132)(465)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_2\alpha_6} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (135462)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_3\alpha_6} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (132465)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_4\alpha_6} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (165432)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_5\alpha_6} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (162435)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_6\alpha_6} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (165)(432)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_7\alpha_6} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (162)(435)$$

$$(A \times B)^{f_8\alpha_6} = \left((1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3) \right) = (135)(462)$$

The elements of wreath product are:

{(e), (14), (25), (36), (1245), (1542), (1346), (1643), (2356), (2653), (123456), (165432), (126453), (135462), (156423), (132465), (153426), (162435), (12)(45)(36), (14)(25)(36), (15)(42)(36), (13)(46)(25), (16)(43)(25), (14)(23)(56), (14)(26)(53), (12)(45), (14)(25), (15)(42), (13)(46), (16)(43), (14)(36), (25)(36), (23)(56), (26)(53), (123)(456), (132)(465), (153)(426), (135)(462), (126)(453), (162)(435), (156)(423), (165)(432), (2356)(14), (2653)(14), (1346)(25), (1643)(25), (1245)(36), (1542)(36).}

5. Stabilizer of $\vec{S}_{3(a,b)}$ in $A \times B$:

The stabilizer of any point (a, b) in $A \times B$ denoted by $\vec{S}_{3(a,b)}$ is given by

$$\vec{S}_{3(a,b)} = \{ f\alpha | (a, b)^{f\alpha} = (a, b) \}$$

Remark:5.1. $\vec{S}_{3(a,b)}$ is a subgroup of $\vec{S}_3$ of order 8

Stabilizer of (1, 1) :

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{S}_{3(1,1)} &= \{ f_1\alpha_1, f_2\alpha_1, f_3\alpha_1, f_8\alpha_1, f_1\alpha_4, f_2\alpha_4, f_3\alpha_4, f_8\alpha_4 \} \\ &= \{ (f_1, f_2, f_3, f_8, (1)), (f_1, f_2, f_3, f_8, (23)) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Stabilizer of (1, 2) :

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{S}_{3(1,2)} &= \{ f_1\alpha_1, f_2\alpha_1, f_4\alpha_1, f_7\alpha_1, f_1\alpha_3, f_2\alpha_3, f_4\alpha_3, f_7\alpha_3 \} \\ &= \{ (f_1, f_2, f_4, f_7, (1)), (f_1, f_2, f_4, f_7, (13)) \} \end{aligned}$$

Stabilizer of (1, 3) :

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{S}_{3(1,3)} &= \{ f_1\alpha_1, f_3\alpha_1, f_4\alpha_1, f_6\alpha_1, f_1\alpha_2, f_3\alpha_2, f_4\alpha_2, f_6\alpha_2 \} \\ &= \{ (f_1, f_3, f_4, f_6, (1)), (f_1, f_3, f_4, f_6, (12)) \} \end{aligned}$$

Stabilizer of (2, 1) :

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{S}_{3(2,1)} &= \{ f_1\alpha_1, f_2\alpha_1, f_3\alpha_1, f_8\alpha_1, f_1\alpha_4, f_2\alpha_4, f_3\alpha_4, f_8\alpha_4 \} \\ &= \{ (f_1, f_2, f_3, f_8, (1)), (f_1, f_2, f_3, f_8, (23)) \}\end{aligned}$$

Stabilizer of (2, 2) :

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{S}_{3(2,2)} &= \{ f_1\alpha_1, f_2\alpha_1, f_4\alpha_1, f_7\alpha_1, f_1\alpha_3, f_2\alpha_3, f_4\alpha_3, f_7\alpha_3 \} \\ &= \{ (f_1, f_2, f_4, f_7, (1)), (f_1, f_2, f_4, f_7, (13)) \}\end{aligned}$$

Stabilizer of (2, 3) :

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{S}_{3(2,3)} &= \{ f_1\alpha_1, f_3\alpha_1, f_4\alpha_1, f_6\alpha_1, f_1\alpha_2, f_3\alpha_2, f_4\alpha_2, f_6\alpha_2 \} \\ &= \{ (f_1, f_3, f_4, f_6, (1)), (f_1, f_3, f_4, f_6, (12)) \}\end{aligned}$$

Remark:5.2. Stabilizers are pairwise equal. That is,

$$\vec{S}_{3(1,1)} = \vec{S}_{3(2,1)}, \vec{S}_{3(1,2)} = \vec{S}_{3(2,2)} \text{ and } \vec{S}_{3(1,3)} = \vec{S}_{3(2,3)}$$

6. Orbit of a point (a, b) of A × B :

For orbit of $(a, b) \in A \times B$, we have $|O(a, b)| = |\vec{S}_3|/|\vec{S}_{3(a,b)}| = 48/8 = 6$

Thus,

$$O(1, 1) = \{(1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 1), (2, 2), (2, 3)\} = A \times B$$

as it can be observed that,

$$(1, 1)^{f_1\alpha_1} = (1, 1)^{f_2\alpha_1} = (1, 1)^{f_3\alpha_1} = (1, 1)^{f_8\alpha_1} = (1, 1)^{f_1\alpha_4} = (1, 1)^{f_2\alpha_4} = (1, 1)^{f_3\alpha_4} = (1, 1)^{f_8\alpha_4} = (1, 1)$$

$$(1, 1)^{f_1\alpha_2} = (1, 1)^{f_2\alpha_2} = (1, 1)^{f_3\alpha_2} = (1, 1)^{f_8\alpha_2} = (1, 1)^{f_1\alpha_5} = (1, 1)^{f_2\alpha_5} = (1, 1)^{f_3\alpha_5} = (1, 1)^{f_8\alpha_5} = (1, 2)$$

$$(1, 1)^{f_1\alpha_3} = (1, 1)^{f_2\alpha_3} = (1, 1)^{f_3\alpha_3} = (1, 1)^{f_8\alpha_3} = (1, 1)^{f_1\alpha_6} = (1, 1)^{f_2\alpha_6} = (1, 1)^{f_3\alpha_6} = (1, 1)^{f_8\alpha_6} = (1, 3)$$

$$(1, 1)^{f_4\alpha_1} = (1, 1)^{f_5\alpha_1} = (1, 1)^{f_6\alpha_1} = (1, 1)^{f_7\alpha_1} = (1, 1)^{f_4\alpha_4} = (1, 1)^{f_5\alpha_4} = (1, 1)^{f_6\alpha_4} = (1, 1)^{f_7\alpha_4} = (2, 1)$$

$$(1, 1)^{f_4\alpha_2} = (1, 1)^{f_5\alpha_2} = (1, 1)^{f_6\alpha_2} = (1, 1)^{f_7\alpha_2} = (1, 1)^{f_4\alpha_5} = (1, 1)^{f_5\alpha_5} = (1, 1)^{f_6\alpha_5} = (1, 1)^{f_7\alpha_5} = (2, 2)$$

$$(1, 1)^{f_4\alpha_3} = (1, 1)^{f_5\alpha_3} = (1, 1)^{f_6\alpha_3} = (1, 1)^{f_7\alpha_3} = (1, 1)^{f_4\alpha_6} = (1, 1)^{f_5\alpha_6} = (1, 1)^{f_6\alpha_6} = (1, 1)^{f_7\alpha_6} = (2, 3)$$

Further, for $\vec{S}_3$ acting on $A \times B$, we observe that;

- The permutation group is nothing but $\vec{S}_3$ itself.
- $\vec{S}_3$ is faithful on $A \times B$.
- $\vec{S}_3$ is imprimitive on $A \times B$. The subsets of imprimitivity are (1, 4)(2, 5) and (3, 6).

References

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